

AGE-RELATED PSYCHOLOGICAL AND PEDAGOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS FOR FOSTERING INITIATIVE.

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of young schoolchildren (7-10 years old) and highlights the factors influencing the formation of initiative qualities in them. Methods and conditions for the development of initiative in the educational process are also described.

Input

One of the main tasks of today's educational process is the formation of a creative, active, and proactive personality. Especially in primary school students, the formation of initiative creates a solid foundation for the development of future independent learning, social activity, and responsibility. In this process, it is important to deeply study the psychological and pedagogical characteristics of this age period, to properly organize educational work.

Psychological characteristics of primary school students. Strength and lability of interest. Although interest in 1st-4th grade students is very active, it is not stable. They quickly immerse themselves in new activities, but inappropriate activities immediately cause a feeling of fatigue or boredom. Therefore, in the process of fostering initiative, it is necessary to organize activities in a form rich in games, research, and experience.

A tendency to imitate. Children of this age easily accept the behavior of adults and peers. The teacher's initiative and creative approach serve as an example for students. Therefore, the activity of the teacher's personality is an important factor that motivates the child to act independently.

Need for emotional sensitivity and positive stimulation. The attitude of younger students towards learning activities largely depends on their emotional state. In them, positive emotions such as joy, interest, and motivation serve as a powerful motivator. Teacher's methods such as praise, encouragement, and support strongly influence the formation of initiative.

Development of imagination and fantasy. At this age, imagination, fantasy, and creativity develop most actively. For the formation of initiative, such activities as creative tasks, model making, storytelling, role-playing games are very effective.

Formation of volitional qualities. The student still encounters difficulties in the process of making independent decisions, making choices, and completing the work. Therefore, the teacher's ability to make simple choices, to independently perform small tasks, develops initiative.

Increased social activity. At primary school age, a child strives to express themselves in the community, to have a position among peers. This creates favorable conditions for showing initiative in collective tasks and the formation of leadership qualities.

Pedagogical characteristics and conditions for the formation of initiative. The playful nature of learning activities. It is important to organize the process of primary education in playful, interactive forms in accordance with the level of development of children. The game element creates a real opportunity for the student to freely express their opinion and propose new ideas.

The leading role of the teacher's personality. Primary school students are strongly attached to the teacher's personality. The teacher's initiative, creativity, and communication culture encourage students to be active. Therefore, the teacher should create conditions for initiative and value every idea of the students.

A strong need for practical activity. Children more successfully acquire knowledge through visual, practical, and experimental tasks. More tasks like "try it yourself," "make the shape," "create a mini project" strengthen initiative skills.

The importance of the incentive and motivation system. Children consider even a small achievement a great success. Proper implementation of incentives (praise, sticker, star, granting additional rights) encourages students to freely express their opinion and make independent decisions.

Formation of communication and speech skills. At this age, students are still inexperienced in the precise expression of speech and thought. The teacher develops children's speech activity and paves the way for initiative through tasks such as small presentations, defending their opinion, and asking questions.

The need for an individual approach. Every child has their own unique character. Giving additional confidence to shy, timid students and offering more complex tasks to active students ensures the development of initiative in a way that suits each student.

Methods that help develop initiative

- **Game technologies:** role-playing games, problem-solving.
- **Project activities:** group mini-projects, elements of research.
- **Creative exercises:** drawing, modeling, storytelling, dramatization.
- **Problem-based learning:** competitive tasks, open-ended questions.
- **Means of music and art:** initiative increases through the activation of creative thinking.
- **Praise and encouragement:** points, stickers, "most active student"

Conclusion

The formation of initiative in primary school students is a complex, but necessary pedagogical process. The educational process, organized taking into account the psychological (interest, imagination, emotionality, imitation) and pedagogical (game activity, motivation, practical tasks, communicative development) characteristics of this age period, allows students to:

- independent thinking,
- creativity,
- social activity,

- confidence in oneself,
- responsibility develops to a strong degree.

The early formation of initiative serves as the foundation for the student's successful learning and acquisition of life competencies in the future.

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